

Supplementary Information

Strong CO₂ adsorption in narrow-pore ADOR zeolites: A combined experimental and computational study on IPC-12 and related structures

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Synthesis of zeolites

Synthesis of parent germanosilicate zeolites

UTL zeolite was synthesized according to Ref.¹ Typically, a certain amount of germanium oxide was dissolved in DMADH ((6R,10S)-6,10-dimethyl-5-azoniaspiro[4,5] decane hydroxide) aqueous solution. Silica (Cab-O-Sil M5) was added progressively to the solution, and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. A gel with the composition of 0.66 SiO₂: 0.33 GeO₂: 0.25 DMAD: 30 H₂O was autoclaved at 448 K for 6 days under agitation (60 rpm). The obtained solid product was recovered by filtration, washed with distilled water, and dried overnight at 363 K. To remove the SDA, the as-synthesized zeolite was calcined at 823 K for 6 h with a temperature ramp of 2 K/min under air flow (200 ml/min).

UOV zeolite was synthesized according to Ref.² using decamethonium dihydroxide (DMDH) as SDA. DMDH was prepared from the commercially available decamethonium dibromide (TCI Europe N.V.) by ion exchange with Ambersep® 900(OH) anion exchange resin. The solution of DMDH was concentrated at $p = 25$ mmHg and $T = 303$ K to reach the concentration of DMDH ~ 1.5 M. A gel with the composition of 0.33 SiO₂: 0.66 GeO₂: 0.25 DMDH: 10 H₂O was autoclaved at 448 K for 7 days under static conditions. The solid product was recovered and calcined as above.

Synthesis of IPC-n zeolites

IPC-n zeolites were synthesized using the ADOR strategy described in Ref.³

IPC-4 and IPC-2 zeolites were synthesized according to Ref.⁴ For that, calcined **UTL** was hydrolyzed in 0.1 M HCl with the w/w ratio of 1/200 at 298 K overnight to produce IPC-1P layered precursor. The product was isolated by centrifugation, washed with water, and dried at ambient temperature.

For the synthesis of IPC-4, 1g of IPC-1P was treated with 20 g of neat octylamine at 333 K for 16 h. The solid was isolated by centrifugation, decantation of the supernatant, and drying in an open tube in the air at 363 K. The sample was calcined at 823 K for 6 h with a temperature ramp of 2 K/min under air flow (200 ml/min).

For the synthesis of IPC-2, 1 g of IPC-1P was added to 10 ml of 1 M HNO₃ solution containing 0.2 g of diethoxydimethylsilane Si(OCH₂CH₃)₂(CH₃)₂. The mixture was heated at 448 K for 16 h in an autoclave. The solid product was isolated, washed with distilled water, and calcined at 823 K for 6 h with a temperature ramp of 2 K/min under air flow (200 ml/min).

IPC-9 and IPC-10 were synthesized according to Ref.⁵. For the synthesis of IPC-9, direct intercalation was performed using a 50% water solution of choline hydroxide. The choline hydroxide was prepared by ion exchange of choline chloride 50% water solution using Ambersep® 900 resin (100 g of resin per 100 g of solution). Then, 1 g of zeolite precursor IPC-1P was mixed with 30 g of choline hydroxide solution and stirred for 4 h at room temperature. Solid IPC-9P was centrifuged, washed with water, centrifuged again, and dried in the oven at 333 K. IPC-9P was calcined at 823 K for 6 h with a temperature ramp of 2 K/min under air flow (200 ml/min).

For the synthesis of IPC-10, a 0.1 g of IPC-9P was introduced to a 25 ml Teflon-lined autoclave. Then, 0.05 g of diethoxydimethylsilane and 10 ml of 1M HNO₃ were added. The autoclave was kept in the oven without agitation for 16 h at 448 K. The product was filtered, washed with water (100 ml), and dried in the oven at 333 K. The sample was calcined as above.

IPC-12 zeolite was synthesized according to Ref. ⁶. Calcined UOV zeolite was treated with 12 M HCl with the w/w ratio of 1/100 at room temperature for 12 h. The solid was isolated by centrifugation, washed with methanol and acetone, dried, and calcined as above.

The role of Ge in the synthesis of zeolites

The addition of Ge into the reaction mixture significantly influences the synthesis of a specific type of germanosilicate zeolite. Corma and Patarin, independently, synthesized germanosilicate zeolite UTL (also known as ITQ-15 and IM-12)⁷⁻⁸ with a substantial amount of Ge as the first 14-12-ring zeolite, due to the structure-directing properties of Ge. It's noteworthy that most of these zeolites could not be formed without Ge. The analysis of the structure revealed a preference for Ge atoms to be situated in double-four-rings (d4r) that link silicate layers. Further experiments led to the synthesis of isomorphously substituted UTL zeolite⁹ or other germanosilicates of various structural forms.¹⁰ Apart from directing the zeolite structures, Ge also contributes to the destabilization of the resulting zeolites due to the vulnerability of the Ge-O bonds after template removal. It has been observed that even exposure to humidity can disrupt the Ge-O bonds, potentially compromising the structure of the germanosilicate zeolite if Ge is largely present in the structure. This hydrolysis proceeds in pure water, and its rate can be moderated by the introduction of acids like HCl or HNO₃. This process is not exclusive to UTL zeolite but has also been demonstrated in other structural types such as ITH, ITR, and IWR.¹¹

The acidic condition hydrolyzes the Si-O-Ge bonds predominantly in the d4r units, aiding the disassembly of the original zeolite into layers. These layers are subsequently reassembled into a new zeolite by reverse assembly during calcination, forming new Si-O-Si bonds and H₂O. Consequently, most of the Ge atoms removed from the framework do not result in a defect site in the final zeolite. Nonetheless, the possibility of the presence of some internal defect sites containing silanol clusters in ADOR zeolites cannot be dismissed. However, the interaction of carbon dioxide with silanols and silanol nests is relatively weak. Numerous reports exist on silicate materials rich in silanols, including zeolites. The interaction of CO₂ with the polar OH group is dependent on the acidity (polarity) of O-H. It can be stated that the specific interaction of CO₂ with O-H groups does not exceed adsorption heats equal to 28 kJ/mol for silanols, such as those on the surface of mesoporous silicas,¹² 30 kJ/mol for weakly acidic Al-OH in Al-SBA-15,¹³ and for strongly acidic Bronsted centers in zeolites ranging from 25-33 kJ/mol.¹⁴ In the case of internal silanols in ADOR zeolites, the heat would be below 30 kJ/mol, which is significantly less than the heat recorded in our experiments. These findings are consistent with the results of theoretical calculations performed on ADOR zeolite models in their pure silica forms, reflecting solely the impact of the local environment's geometry and confined space.

Characterization

XRD

The phase purity and structure of zeolite samples under study were determined by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Bruker AXS-D8 Advance diffractometer with a graphite monochromator and a position-sensitive detector (Vântec-1) using CuK α radiation in Bragg-Brentano geometry at a scan rate of 0.25° 2 θ /min. Before the measurements, the samples were ground gently and packed into the holder to decrease the effect of the preferential orientation of individual crystals.

SEM/EDX

The size and shape of synthesized materials were evaluated by scanning electron microscopy images using a JEOL JSM-7500F instrument with a cold cathode-field emission (parameters of measurements: 1 kV, GB high mode) (UTL-based) and using Lyra 3 instrument (Tescan, Czech Republic) (UOV-derived materials). The quantitative elemental composition of the materials was further evaluated using a scanning electron microscope (LYRA 3, Tescan, Brno-Kohoutovice, Czech Republic) equipped with EDX analyser Aztec X-Max 20 (Oxford Instruments, England) at an acceleration voltage of 20 kV.

Ar adsorption/desorption isotherms

Specific surface area and pore volume and size of investigated samples were measured using argon adsorption/desorption at a temperature of liquid argon (87 K) by using ASAP 2020 equipment (Micromeritics, USA) (UTL, IPC-2, IPC-4, IPC-9 and IPC-10) and 3Flex (Micromeritics, USA) (UOV and IPC-12). Before each adsorption measurement, the sample was degassed to allow a slow removal of most of the pre-adsorbed water at low temperatures. This was done to avoid potential structural damage to the sample due to surface tension effects and hydrothermal alteration. Starting at ambient temperature the sample was degassed at 383 K (temperature ramp of 0.5 K/min) until the residual pressure of 10⁻² mmHg was attained. After further heating at 383 K for 1 hour the temperature was increased (temperature ramp of 1 K/min) until the temperature of 523 K was achieved. The sample was degassed at this temperature for 8 hours under a turbomolecular pump vacuum. The specific surface area was calculated according to the BET method.¹⁵⁻¹⁶ The BET surface area was evaluated by using adsorption data in the relative argon pressure range $x > 0.05$ until the slope of the so-called Rouquerol's plot *i.e.* $n_{ads} \cdot (1-x)$ vs x is positive.¹⁷ The pore size distribution and micropore volumes were determined by the NL-DFT method employing Ar@87K on H-zeolite kernel included in SAIEUS software package (Micromeritics, USA). The external surface area was determined by modified (three-parameter) BET equation.

$$n_{ads} = n_{\mu}^0 + \frac{n_{ml} C x}{(1-x)[1+(C-1)x]} \quad (S1)$$

where n_{μ}^0 is net molar amount of adsorbate which fills the micropores, n_{ml} is molar amount of adsorbate need for formation statistical monolayer, C is equilibrium constant, x is relative pressure ($x = p/p_0$, p_0 is adsorbate saturated vapour at temperature of measurement).¹⁸

XRD patterns of both parent germanosilicates and IPC-n zeolites matched well with those reported in the literature indicating a high degree of crystallinity and phase purity (Fig. S1).^{6, 19-20} The common topology of the layers in the UTL and derived IPC-n zeolites (Fig. S1A) and UOV and IPC-12 (Fig. S1B) is reflected in the same profile of intra-layer reflections (reflections with Miller indices $0kl$) (marked with asterisks in Fig. S1).

Fig. S1. XRD patterns of (A) parent UTL and UTL-derived IPC-n zeolites; (B) UOV and UOV-derived IPC-12 zeolite.

Fig. S2. Ar adsorption isotherms of parent **UTL** and **UTL**-derived **IPC-n** zeolites in linear scale (A) and semi-logarithmic scale (C); **UOV** and **UOV**-derived **IPC-12** zeolite in linear scale (B) and semi-logarithmic scale (D)

All zeolites under the study show argon adsorption isotherms of type I based on the IUPAC nomenclature, characteristic of purely microporous materials (Fig. S2). The low-pressure region of the isotherms exhibits well recognizable steps of primary pore filling (see Fig. S2 C,D). This filling reflects the variation in the pore size of investigated zeolites (Fig. S3). The order of the studied materials according to the pore size is as follows: **UTL** > **UOV** > **IPC-12** > **IPC-2** \approx **IPC-10** \approx **IPC-9** > **IPC-4**. The textural characteristics of the materials are summarized in Table S1.

Fig. S3. Pore size distribution curve of (A) parent **UTL** and **UTL**-derived **IPC-n** zeolites; (B) **UOV** and **UOV**-derived **IPC-12** zeolite

Table S1. Textural characteristics and composition (Si/Ge ratio) of investigated zeolites

Zeolite	S_{BET} m² g⁻¹	S_{ext} m² g⁻¹	V_{micro} cm³ g⁻¹	V_{tot} cm³ g⁻¹	Si/Ge
UTL	480	14	0.175	0.193	3
IPC-2	370	44	0.133	0.184	60
IPC-4	219	9	0.079	0.091	65
IPC-9	150	96	0.021	0.154	189
IPC-10	271	89	0.069	0.174	294
UOV	430	33	0.154	0.241	4
IPC-12	430	76	0.148	0.249	90

Fig. S4. SEM micrographs of the zeolites investigated. (A) UTL, (B) IPC-2 (OKO), (C) IPC-4 (PCR), (D) IPC-9, (E) IPC-10, (F) UOV, (G) IPC-12

The SEM images of all samples show plate-like crystallites typical for materials with layered structure. This demonstrates the preservation of the morphology of the original crystals during the ADOR process.

Fig. S5. Low pressure region of adsorption isotherms of carbon dioxide on (A): parent **UTL** and **UTL**-derived IPC-n zeolites; (B) **UOV** and **UOV**-derived IPC-12 zeolite at 298 K

Spatial Decomposition of Adsorption Heats

As the pore volume is made of compartments, which may or may not be accessible, it is beneficial to report the adsorption heat for a given compartment and include the populations/weights, so that for any combination of accessible compartments the overall heat can be estimated. Our definition of compartments is based on accessibility, so that space of similar entrance restrictions is evaluated together. As a compartment 1, we take the easily accessible volume. Some zeolites contain only this type of pore space. The compartments 2 and 3 are reserved for a volume, which may be difficult to sample.

For materials based on the parent zeolites **UTL** and ***CTH**, the compartment 2 is the side channel (when its entrance window aperture is small); in case of IPC-6 it is the side channel of the **PCR**-like layer. The definition of compartments in some more intricate systems is given in Figure S6.

Fig. S6. Definition of compartments in selected materials. CO₂ sampling depicted for illustration of the pore system. (Si blue, O red, easily accessible volume – compartment 1 – light blue, volumes with restricted access – compartment 2 and 3 – in orange and purple, respectively. In some cases, a different cell setting was used than in the reported cif files).

Table S2. Adsorption heat of carbon dioxide (in kJ/mol) at the **DFT/CC** level in various materials (importance sampling with AIFF used as the biasing potential). The overall value given, but also a decomposition into “compartments”. Besides the adsorption heat (q), the standard deviation (std) and weight/population (w) given.

				Compartment 1			Compartment 2			Compartment 3		
		q	std	q	std	w	q	std	w	q	std	w
UTL												
-S4R	IPC-2 (OKO)	22.8	4.0	22.8	4.0	1.00						
	IPC-10	24.8	3.8	21.9	2.1	0.48	27.5	3.0	0.52			
	IPC-10 mono	26.5	4.8	22.6	2.5	0.46	29.8	3.7	0.54			
-D4R	IPC-4 (PCR)	29.8	3.3	29.2	3.0	0.47	30.4	3.5	0.53			
	IPC-9	29.4	3.0	28.6	2.6	0.69	31.3	3.2	0.31			
-DIS	IPC-6 (*PCS)	27.0	4.7	25.8	5.0	0.66	29.2	2.9	0.34			
	IPC-7	21.8	4.6	21.8	4.6	1.00						
UOV												
-S4R		28.1	6.7	23.6	3.8	0.59	34.5	4.3	0.41			
-D4R	IPC-12	37.9	6.7	21.4	2.6	0.10	39.8	3.8	0.90			
*CTH												
-S4R	IPC-16	22.9	2.4	22.6	2.0	0.96	29.1	3.0	0.04			
	IPC-16 alt	24.5	2.8	24.4	2.6	0.97	28.6	3.9	0.03			
-D4R	IPC-15	33.9	3.9	33.9	3.9	1.00						
IWR												
-S4R	IPC-17	23.4	3.6	23.4	3.6	1.00						
-D4R		28.0	7.2	21.5	2.6	0.49	34.3	3.9	0.51			
IWW												
-S4R	IPC-18	24.9	4.0	23.8	3.1	0.83	30.1	3.7	0.17			
-D4R		29.3	6.2	22.1	3.6	0.31	32.9	4.0	0.57	30.9	3.2	0.11

Table S3. Adsorption heat of carbon dioxide (in kJ/mol) at the **PBE-D2** level in various materials (importance sampling with AIFF used as the biasing potential). The overall value given, but also a decomposition into “compartments”. Besides the adsorption heat (q), the standard deviation (std) and weight/population (w) given.

				Compartment 1			Compartment 2			Compartment 3		
		q	std	q	std	w	q	std	w	q	std	w
UTL												
-S4R	IPC-2 (OKO)	21.5	3.7	21.5	3.7	1.00						
	IPC-10	23.6	3.7	20.9	2.1	0.50	26.2	3.0	0.50			
	IPC-10 mono	25.0	4.6	21.5	2.4	0.48	28.3	3.6	0.52			
-D4R	IPC-4 (PCR)	28.6	3.2	28.2	3.0	0.49	28.9	3.4	0.51			
	IPC-9	28.4	3.0	27.7	2.6	0.71	30.2	3.2	0.29			
-DIS	IPC-6 (*PCS)	25.5	4.7	24.4	4.9	0.68	27.8	2.9	0.32			
	IPC-7	20.4	4.3	20.4	4.3	1.00						
UOV												
-S4R		26.3	6.4	22.6	3.8	0.64	33.0	4.3	0.36			
-D4R	IPC-12	35.9	7.0	20.5	2.6	0.13	38.2	3.8	0.87			
*CTH												
-S4R	IPC-16	21.7	2.2	21.5	2.0	0.97	27.2	3.2	0.03			
	IPC-16 alt	23.4	2.8	23.2	2.6	0.96	27.9	3.8	0.04			
-D4R	IPC-15	32.3	3.9	32.3	3.9	1.00						
IWR												
-S4R	IPC-17	22.5	3.3	22.5	3.3	1.00						
-D4R		26.1	6.9	20.5	2.6	0.55	32.8	3.9	0.45			
IWW												
-S4R	IPC-18	23.7	4.0	22.7	3.1	0.84	29.1	3.7	0.16			
-D4R		27.6	6.2	21.0	3.6	0.35	31.5	4.0	0.52	30.2	3.3	0.13

Table S4. Adsorption heat of carbon dioxide (in kJ/mol) at the **AIFF** level in various materials. The overall value given, but also a decomposition into “compartments”. Besides the adsorption heat (q), the standard deviation (std) and weight/population (w) given.

				Compartment 1			Compartment 2			Compartment 3		
		q	std	q	std	w	q	std	w	q	std	w
UTL												
-S4R	IPC-2 (OKO)	23.5	4.2	23.5	4.2	1.00						
	IPC-10	26.6	4.5	22.2	2.3	0.39	29.5	3.1	0.61			
	IPC-10 mono	26.3	4.5	22.8	2.5	0.48	29.5	3.3	0.52			
-D4R	IPC-4 (PCR)	29.5	3.1	29.3	3.2	0.51	29.7	3.1	0.49			
	IPC-9	30.3	3.0	29.2	2.6	0.64	32.2	2.8	0.36			
-DIS	IPC-6 (*PCS)	27.3	4.6	26.3	5.0	0.67	29.4	2.7	0.33			
	IPC-7	22.4	4.7	22.4	4.7	1.00						
UOV												
-S4R		27.4	5.6	25.1	4.4	0.70	32.8	4.2	0.30			
-D4R	IPC-12	43.6	5.5	22.9	3.3	0.04	44.4	3.6	0.96	26.7	3.7	0.00
*CTH												
-S4R	IPC-16	23.0	2.6	22.7	2.1	0.96	30.5	3.7	0.04			
	IPC-16 alt	29.3	6.9	24.5	2.5	0.63	37.3	3.4	0.37			
-D4R	IPC-15	33.0	3.4	33.0	3.4	1.00						
IWR												
-S4R	IPC-17	24.9	3.3	24.9	3.3	1.00						
-D4R		35.4	7.4	22.5	3.1	0.20	38.6	3.8	0.80			
IWW												
-S4R	IPC-18	26.0	4.4	24.9	3.7	0.81	31.0	3.6	0.19			
-D4R		36.7	6.1	24.1	4.6	0.11	38.6	4.0	0.82	33.3	3.2	0.07

Table S5. Comparison of calculated heats of adsorption ($T = 300$ K) of CO_2 with experimental values of Zukal et al.²¹ Zero-coverage limit, the heats are given in kJ/mol.

Material	AIFF	PBE-D2 ^a	DFT/CC ^a	Zukal et al.
IPC-7	22.4	20.4	21.8	25
IPC-2 (OKO) – $C2/m$	23.5	21.5	22.8	27 ^b
IPC-2 (OKO) – $P-1$	26.5 ^c	23.5 ^{a,c}	25.3 ^{a,c}	
IPC-6	27.3	25.5	27.0	27
IPC-4 (PCR)	29.5	28.6	29.8	29

^a A value from importance sampling, based on the AIFF sampling.

^b Symmetry of the samples was not explicitly stated.

^c Heat of adsorption in **OKO** calculated on the experimental P-1 structure²² instead of the PBE-D2 structure in the highest possible symmetry ($C2/m$). The increase of adsorption heat from PBE-D2 ($C2/m$) to experimental (P-1) structure is predicted also by CFF (from 22.8 to 23.8),²³ CCFF (from 24.4 to 30.4)²⁴ and TraPPE-zeo (from 22.0 to 24.0) potentials.²⁵⁻²⁶

Binding motives

Fig. S7. The CO₂ binding in the entrance window of IPC-10. A view from the (a) main channel (12MR) and (b) side channel (9MR) direction.

Fig. S8. CO₂ interaction energy map in IPC-10 (structures from importance sampling) – PBE interaction energy, CC correction and the overall interaction energy (PBE/CC). Interaction energy in kJ/mol, a color scale for each component of interaction energy given. Framework indicated as wireframe model (Si orange, O red). The two vertical tube-like objects are the sampling in the main channel, whereas the two constricted spaces are the side (9MR) channels.

Fig. S9. CO₂ interaction energy map in PCR (structures from importance sampling) – PBE interaction energy, CC correction and the overall interaction energy (PBE/CC). Interaction energy in kJ/mol, a color scale for each component of interaction energy given. Framework indicated as wireframe model (Si orange, O red). The main channel on the left and right side. The PCR cavity (8MR channel) is on top and bottom of the cell (divided by the periodic boundary conditions).

Fig. S10. CO₂ interaction energy map in IPC-6 (structures from importance sampling) – PBE interaction energy, CC correction and the overall interaction energy (PBE/CC). Interaction energy in kJ/mol, a color scale for each component of interaction energy given. Framework indicated as wireframe model (Si orange, O red). The **OKO**-like pore system is on the top and bottom of the cell, the **PCR**-like pore system is in the central part of the cell.

Ab initio MD study of CO₂ in the binding motif of IPC-12

The adsorption heat in narrow areas of the material can be affected by vibrations of the lattice. To address this issue, short ab initio molecular dynamics (AIMD) of CO₂ in the cage of IPC-12 was performed in VASP.²⁷ During the first 2 ps (1 fs timestep), we slowly heated the system up to the target temperature 298 K. In this initial stage of equilibration, the molecule changed its orientation from the ideal arrangement (i.e., parallel to the prolonged side of the cage; see Fig. 5a in the main article) to molecule heading towards the 8MR entrance of the cage (see Figure S12; the state after the equilibration is denoted as $t = 0$ ps). Then, 12 ps of simulation at 298 K followed. In the first 4 ps, the molecule was clearly still equilibrating, and thus initial equilibration of 2 ps was insufficient. After that the CO₂ reaches an optimal configuration and remains in a similar state for the rest of simulation (i.e. 8 ps) (Figure S13). We estimated the interaction energy as a function of simulation time using Equation S2. In Equation S2, E_{Int0} is the interaction energy estimate, $E_{IPC-12+CO_2}$ is the potential energy of the adsorbent-adsorbate system at a given time, whereas E_{IPC-12} and E_{CO_2} are the energies of adsorbent and adsorbate in the same configuration as in the adsorbate-adsorbent system. This way, the deformation energy contribution to the interaction energy is neglected. The heat of adsorption in this particular cavity estimated from the last 7.5 ps of the simulation is 39.7 kJ/mol, only slightly lower than the 40.7 kJ/mol reported using the rigid framework simulation (Fig. 5b). Such result justifies the use of rigid framework for estimation of adsorption heat, as the lattice vibrations do not significantly affect the results even for as confined space as the IPC-12 binding motif. The value of 39.7 kJ/mol was calculated using DFT/CC applied to small set of structures taken from AIMD at the PBE-D2 level.

Fig. S11. Snapshots from the AIMD of CO₂ in IPC-12 binding motif.

$$E_{Int0}(t) = E_{IPC-12+CO_2}(t) - E_{IPC-12}(t) - E_{CO_2}(t) \quad (S2)$$

Fig. S12. Interaction energy (without deformation) as a function of simulation time.

Models and Potentials

The model of CO₂ used in AIFF simulations is a modified version of that obtained using the Antechamber tool.²⁸⁻²⁹ For the CO₂ molecule the C-O bond length was 1.1724 Å, O-C-O angle was 180 deg. The CO₂ structure was treated having positive charge on carbon and two negative charges of half of the magnitude on oxygen atoms. Note, that the adsorbate charges were optimized to reproduce the interaction energy with the framework at the zero-coverage limit, and thus not necessarily describe adsorbate – adsorbate interaction as accurately. The ideal partial charges for the zero-coverage case depend on the framework charges and satisfy the condition $q_{Si} \cdot q_C = 0.899$ (electroneutrality of both the molecule and the framework as well as positive charge on silicon atom is assumed). The intramolecular electrostatics and vdW interaction were excluded for all the gasses.

The CO₂ was described using the following analytic expression

$$V(r) = V_{elst} + Ar^{-1} + Br^{-6} + Cr^{-12} + D2(s_6) \quad (S3)$$

where V_{elst} represents the electrostatic potential.

Table S6. Carbon dioxide – zeolite AIFF parameters (partial charges mentioned above)

Interaction	A	B	C	s ₆
Potential	[kJ mol ⁻¹ nm ¹]	[kJ mol ⁻¹ nm ⁶]	[kJ mol ⁻¹ nm ¹²]	
O – C	-7.239E-05	-3.151E-04	1.214E-06	0.8578
O – O	-6.391E-04	-1.320E-03	1.612E-06	0.4516
Si – C	5.262E-04	-2.129E-06	2.176E-08	0.7956
Si – O	7.651E-04	-7.781E-06	6.188E-08	0.2173

Figure S13 Comparison of CO₂ heats of adsorption from various force fields with the DFT/CC value from importance sampling (for all investigated materials). Also, PBE-D2 estimate from importance sampling is given.

References

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